

INITIAL SPORTS TRAINING FOR YOUNG ATHLETES**Aminov Batir Umidovich**

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Annotation. This article analyzes the importance of the fact that the initial stage of training of young athletes is aimed at physical training of the most important sports.

Keywords: sport, types of sports, study, coach, factor.

The increasing demands of sports on the personality of an athlete predetermined the emergence of the theory of sports orientation, which began to be developed. The purpose of sports orientation is a comprehensive study and identification of individual inclinations (which are the basis for the development of abilities) and the characteristics of those involved who meet the requirements of a particular sport to the maximum extent.

Sports orientation can be considered, according to its theoretical and methodological foundations, as a specific form of professional orientation. Therefore, the basic theoretical prerequisites of professional orientation will be applied in sports selection. There are two approaches to predicting athletic abilities:

- study of the stability of individual levels of development;
- study of the growth rates of indicators.

First of all, this concerns the formation of model (reference) characteristics of athletes, which the coach focuses on when evaluating the prospects of children, as well as the commonality of organizational approaches in selection in various sports. The features and qualities of the first group are mainly limited by constitutional (genetic) factors, while the features and qualities of the second group are mainly in the function of training influence.

In order to successfully predict the development of the most important personality traits and qualities for gaming activity, when selecting research methods, first of all, it is necessary to focus on stable (little changed during development and to a small extent dependent on training influences) factors.

Of considerable interest are the data and the influence of genetic factors on energy capabilities, respiratory abilities, the specifics of the cardiovascular system and especially the maximum oxygen consumption. There is evidence that genetic factors significantly affect the indicators of physical development, body

composition and motor abilities of children. Based on the expert assessment, the following hierarchy of the most important qualities and abilities for the game has been established:

- tactical thinking (the ability to quickly and accurately solve problems of varying degrees of complexity);
- speed of learning various techniques and actions;
- the ability to accurately perform relatively complex motor tasks;
- the ability to quickly adjust their actions with a change in the situation;
- starting speed; remote speed;
- jumping ability; endurance;
- strength qualities.

The first four indicators characterize the athlete's dexterity. The initial level of this quality largely determines the prospects of a young athlete. To correctly determine the most appropriate sports role for a child is a rather difficult and still unresolved problem, i.e. the need to ensure physical education child orientation along with sports selection. The essence of this orientation is to choose the most appropriate type of physical activity for him in the course of learning the "ABC of movements", taking into account his individual characteristics, and to give a conclusion about the preferred forms of physical education with the greatest satisfaction used in the future.

When developing the problem of sports orientation, the conclusion suggests that further development of research should be aimed at developing a methodology for this area of sports science. Currently, methodological principles have been formulated on the problem of sports orientation and selection: determination, dominant trait, development potential.

One of the main points determining the further athletic success of a child is the age at which he starts playing sports and the time of preparation. The age at which you start playing sports determines the time frame for training a high-class athlete. The younger the child, the more time it takes for him to fulfill the standard of a master of sports and a master of sports of international class. The choice of training loads. During the initial training period, the training process only gradually acquires all the features that characterize sports training in its developed form.

The volume of high-intensity exercises increases at a much slower rate than in the future, although the total volume may increase widely. Especially careful should be taken to the magnitude and intensity of loads during the period of intensive growth and maturation of the body. The use of an integrated training

method, including outdoor and sports games, game exercises and tasks, as well as complexes of special preparatory exercises aimed at educating physical abilities that play an important role in sports, is highly effective.

The development of physical qualities, for example, boys aged 9-11, is most effectively achieved when using high-speed exercises aimed at developing speed, strength and speed-strength abilities in a single complex.

References:

1. Balsevich V.K., Methodological principles of research on the problem of selection and sports orientation // Theory and Practice of Physical Culture, 1980, No.1, pp.31-33.
2. Rozmatov, I. E. (2022). Bosque Throwers Sport Many Years Of Work Procedure For Planning. (On The Example Of Athletes Aged 14-16). International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 354-359.
3. Ro'zmatov, I. E. (2022). Bosqon uloqtiruvchilarni mashg'ulot jarayonida kuch jismoniy sifatini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos ahamiyati. Youth, science, education: topical issues, achievements and innovations, 1(7), 17-22.
4. Ro'zmatov, I. E (2022). The importance of the methods used in the development of physical quality of behavior of invading athletes carrying out hard work. Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(12), 325-330.
5. Ro'zmatov, I. E. (2022). Bosqon uloqtirish mashg'ulotlarida maxsus mashqlarni ahamiyati. Youth, science, education: topical issues, achievements and innovations, 1(7), 10-16.
6. Rozmatov, I. E. (2021). The Development Mechanism of Hammer Throwers Technique. Middle European Scientific Bulletin, 19, 158-162.
7. Erkozovich, RI (2023). Bozon otirganlarni o'ylash jarayondagi pedagogik nazorat. Xalqaro jurnali ijtimoiy fan va fanlararo tadqiqot ISSN: 2277-3630 Ta'sir omili: 7.429, 12 (05), 137-143.
8. Ro'zmatov, I., & G'ulomjonov, S. (2023). Qisqa masoflarga turishda maxsus mashg'ulotning motor usullarining o'ziqish ahamiyati. Amaliy fan va texnologiya xalqaro byulleteni , 3 (3), 89-93.
9. Rozmatov, I., & Gulomjonov, S. (2023). The specific importance of motor methods of special training in short-distance running. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(3), 89-93.
10. Umidovich, A. B. (2022). Legal grounds for the development of the sports industry in uzbekistan. Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 46-49.

11. Саруханов, А. А., Азизов, М. А., & Аминов, Б. У. (2023, January). Новые технологии для развития силовых качеств у студентов. In international scientific and practical conference" the time of scientific progress" (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 217-225).
12. Umidovich, A. B. (2023). Unusual volleyball training sessions. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(06), 1-4.
13. Аминов, Б. У. (2023, May). Спортивная подготовка юных спортсменов. In International Conference" Modern Pedagogical and Philological Education Sciences" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 50-56).
14. Aminov, B. U. (2023, May). Talabalarga o'tiladigan jismoniy tarbiya darslaridagi yangiliklar. In international scientific conference" innovative trends in science, practice and education" (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 11-16).
15. Aminov, B. U. (2023, May). Bolalarning suvdan qo'rqmaslikka va sog'lom bo'lib shakllanishida suzishning o'rni. In international scientific and practical conference" the time of scientific progress" (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 23-31).
16. Ilyosovich, M. S. (2023). Improving physical education of students with fatigued health. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(10), 32-35.
17. Ilyosovich, M. S. (2022). History and development of the development of physical education. Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(12), 1-3.
18. Ilyosovich, M. S. (2022). The importance of the laws of education and training in the skins of physical culture. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(10), 260-262.
19. Dexqonov B.B. (2022). Obligations arising from contractual relations in sports (football) law in uzbekistan. Asia pacific journal of marketing & management review issn: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603, 11(11), 62-65.
20. Dexqonov B.B. (2022). The essence of various sports games. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 355-358.
21. Rakhimov, S., & Irmatov, S. (2023). The importance of a healthy lifestyle in adapting to student life. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 3(3), 94-99.

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22. Anvarovich, I. S. (2023). Development of strength endurance qualities among students. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 12(09), 13-15.
23. Айрапетьянц, Л., & Ирматов, Ш. (2013). Проявление право-и левосторонних двигательных функций у баскетболистов в условиях соревновательных игр. Наука в олимпийском спорте, (1), 46-48.
24. Umarova, Z. U., & Ugli, Y. D. N. (2023). Innovative technologies and their application in sports.
25. Umarov, A. A., & Umarova, Z. U. (2023). Talaba-yoshlarni jismoniy sifatlarini rivojlantirishda milliy va harakatli o'yinlarning o'rni. Scientific progress, 4(1), 260-265.
26. Urinboevna, U. Z., Burkhanovich, D. B., & Ismailovna, Y. F. (2022). New technologies for the development of strength qualities Youth. International journal of social science & interdisciplinary research issn: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 220-224.